

Protocol and analysis plan for methodological neurosonography studies

These studies aim to answer basic methodological questions of neurosonography, regarding matters of inter-rater reliability, baseline variability, fluctuations caused by rapid changes in intracranial pressure, and the learning curve for novice operators. These studies will be performed in healthy volunteers as well as in neurointensive-care patients. The studies will start inclusion in November 2025.

The studies will be performed at the Karolinska University Hospital and Karolinska Institutet. The studies will be performed in accordance with the Helsinki declaration and have been approved by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority, diary number 2025-03712-01. These studies were prospectively registered at researchweb.org, diary number 285819.

Sub-study 1. Inter-rater reliability and variability of transcranial doppler.

Hypothesis

Transcranial doppler (TCD) can be performed with an acceptable inter-rater reliability, defined as an Intra-Class Correlation (ICC) of at least 0.75.

Methodology/approach/data analysis

We will perform paired TCD measurements in healthy volunteers and in patients with pathological TCD values. Two raters, blinded to each others measurements, will alternate and perform bilateral TCD measurements on the middle cerebral artery (MCA) and the internal carotid artery (ICA). We will alternate the order of the operators to avoid introducing confounding caused by potential time effects. Pulse and blood pressure will be monitored. After manual TCD measurements, we will also perform robotic TCD measurements of the MCA continuously for five minutes.

The inter-rater reliability between operators and between operators and robot will be visually described with Bland-Altman plots. It will be quantified with ICC and Bland-Altman analysis if the normal distribution assumption is met. If the normal distribution assumption for ICC is not met, we will use Lin's concordance correlation coefficient and 95 percentile interval of the differences instead.

We will explore the within-subject variability in TCD values over the five minutes of robotic measurements. We will provide a group-level summary of the within-subject variability. This will be reported with a mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variability for the within-subject standard deviations, as well as means of the within-subject min and max variations and 95 percentile interval, relative to the within-subject mean. We will use descriptive statistics of periodicity in the within-subject variability. If the normality assumption is not met, we will use non-parametric analyses based on medians and interquartile ranges instead of means and standard deviations.

This study will also explore the agreement between two different methods to measure flow velocities in the ICA, using a linear transducer or a phased-array transducer. This agreement will also be explored with Bland-Altman plots and ICC or CCC, similar to the analysis described above.

In the sample size calculation, we set as our null hypotheses an ICC of 0.5 (a poor agreement) and as our alternative hypotheses an ICC of 0.75 (a good agreement). With power 80% and

the level of significance set at $p=0.05$, this yields a sample size of 36 subjects. We aim to include 40 healthy volunteers and 10 patients with pathological TCD values.

Sub-study 2. Learning curve in optic nerve sheath diameter ultrasound – a prospective pedagogical case report

Hypothesis

It is commonly suggested that 20 independently performed ultrasound exams of the optic nerve sheath diameter (ONSD) is enough to be considered an independent operator. The hypothesis for this study is that self-reported difficulty in image gathering, time to gather images, image quality and agreement with an expert, changes significantly in an operator between being a novice with 20 performed exams and being an intermediate operator with 60 performed exams.

Methodology/approach/data analysis

This case report will follow a novice operator that has recently received initial ONSD sonography training and performed 20 independent exams. The operator will gather data on self-reported difficulty in image acquisition and time to gather images for her ONSD exams, after having completed her initial 20 independent exams during her ONSD training. Image quality will be assessed by an expert operator for the following 40 exams. The expert assessment will be performed for all of these 40 exams in random order with the expert blinded to the order the exams were performed. Self-assessment of difficulty and expert assessment of image quality will be performed according to the protocol provided in appendix 1. In the first 10 exams, the novice operator and an expert operator will perform paired ONSD measurements blinded to each others measurements. Another similar set of 10 paired exams will be performed once again when the operator has performed the additional 40 independent exams. The agreement for these sets of measurements will be separately analyzed with Bland-Altman plots and ICC to describe the variability and potential bias. The mean and median absolute difference will be calculated. These will be compared between the early and the late set of measurements with paired t-test or Wilcoxon signed-rank test, depending on distribution. Trends in image quality and time for image acquisition will be described with descriptive statistics and also compared between the early and late sets of 10 measurements.

This is a hypothesis generating and descriptive case report aimed at describing the learning curve for an ONSD sonography operator in detail. It will also test outcome measurements for future studies of the learning curve in larger groups. No sample size calculation has been performed for this study.

Sub-study 3. Optic nerve sheath diameter changes in rapid changes of intracranial pressure in healthy individuals.

Hypothesis

The optic nerve sheath diameter measured by ultrasound changes significantly and immediately in healthy individuals during head-down tilt.

Methodology/approach/data analysis

This will be a case-crossover study that will include healthy, adult volunteers. Exclusion criteria are ocular disease or previous ocular surgery that hinder acquisition of good quality images with transorbital ultrasound.

The volunteers will assume a resting position, lying down with 30 degrees elevated head of bed, facilitating a good cerebral venous drainage and an intracranial pressure (ICP) assumedly close to 0 mmHg. We will gather images of the optic nerve sheath in both eyes with transorbital ultrasound in this position. We will use a GE Vivid S70 ultrasound machine with an 11L linear

probe. The frequency will be set at 10-12 MHz. We will keep Mechanical Index <0.23 and Thermal Index <1 .

After gathering of images in the 30 degrees position described above, we will re-position the volunteer in a Trendelenburg position with head-down tilt at 13 degrees. This results in an increased cerebral venous stasis, yielding an increase in ICP. After two minutes in the Trendelenburg position we will gather a new set of bilateral images of the optic nerve sheath, and then return the patient to the 30 degrees position. In the 30 degrees position we will immediately gather a new set of images, and then another set three minutes later.

We will measure ONSD internal (ONSDint) and external (ONSDext) of the dura mater in the gathered images afterward. Measurements will be performed by an expert ONSD operator who will be blinded to the identity and sex of the volunteers as well as to the position for each image.

We will perform paired comparisons of ONSD values before, during and after exposure to transient elevation of ICP caused by the Trendelenburg position. Data will be tested for normality with the Shapiro-Wilks test. If data based on this can be assumed to be sampled from a normal distribution, it will be compared with paired t-tests. If data is not normal, it will be compared with paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Data will be analyzed and presented stratified by sex.

We based our sample size calculation on what few previous studies there are of changes in ONSD in rapidly changing ICP. The expected increase in ICP when going from the 30 degrees position to the Trendelenburg position should yield an average ONSD increase of ≥ 0.3 mm. With an ONSD baseline of 6 mm on average, and a standard deviation of 0.3 mm, we would need to include 10 volunteers to test this with a power of 80% and the level of significance set at $p < 0.05$. To account for uncertainties in the findings underlying this sample size calculation, and to allow for comparisons between men and women, we will include up to 20 men and 20 women. This study will be performed alongside sub-study 1 above, including largely the same volunteers.

Ethical considerations

Measurements will be performed in both adult, healthy volunteers and in intensive care patients. The neurosonographic methods used are safe and painless. Volunteers will be well informed about the study and will sign written, informed consent to participate. Private and/or professional relationships between researchers/doctoral students and participants is an issue that will be handled with care to avoid undue influence on potential participants by researchers.

The patients that we will include will, almost without exception, have been admitted due to life-threatening emergencies, making it impossible to obtain informed consent in advance. Due to the nature of the cohort with high morbidity and mortality, many patients cannot give consent afterwards either. The project aims to improve treatment and outcomes for many patients in the future. The studies are observational, using harmless and painless techniques. To the best of our knowledge, no complications related to neurosonography have been reported. Examinations will be discontinued if patients appear stressed by the examination itself, or if there is any risk that the gathering of data interferes with ongoing care or treatments. Data will be stored digitally with two-factor authentication and pseudonymized with a separately stored code key. We hereby meet the conditions for research without informed consent according to the Swedish Ethics Review Act, paragraph 20-22. The studies will be performed in accordance with the Helsinki declaration and have been approved by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority, diary number 2025-03712-01.

Appendix 1 – Expert quality assessment of ONSD image

ON borders 0-4 points (0 - no clear borders on either side, 4 - clear borders on both side):

ONSDint borders 0-4 points (0 - no clear borders on either side, 4 - clear borders on both side):

ONSDext borders 0-4 points (0 - no clear borders on either side, 4 - clear borders on both side):

Length of nerve and sheath clearly visualized, 1 point per 0,5 cm:

Self assessment of ONSD image gathering

Transverse or sagittal view: _____

Time to gather image (seconds): _____

Self-reported difficulty of image acquisition 1-5 (1 very easy, 5 very difficult): _____

Comments: _____
